

Volume 12, Issues 1 & 2, November, 2025

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

A Publication of

**THE DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY AND
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT,
FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES,
UNIVERSITY OF ILORIN,
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VOLUME 12, ISSUES 1&2, NOVEMBER, 2025

ISSN: 1596-4116

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MIGRANT FARMERS' SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS AND PATTERN OF MIGRATION INTO THE RURAL COMMUNITIES OF KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Migration is a critical global issue because of its effect on population distribution and socio-economic development at the point of origin and destination. Migrant farmers play a crucial role in food crop production. This paper examined the migration patterns of farmers from other parts of Nigeria to rural communities of Kwara State, focusing on their purpose, reasons for migration, and the challenges they face in their current rural areas. It utilized a survey data of 825 migrant farmers' heads of households. Descriptive and regression was used for the analysis. The findings revealed that most farmers migrated from Benue State (23%), Sokoto State (10.4%), Borno State (2.9%), with few others from Nigerian states. Key push factors included inadequate farmland, limited economic opportunities, insecurity, conflict, and unemployment in their places of origin. Pull factors at the destination included relative peace, security, availability of arable land, and access to farm inputs, each statistically significant (p -value < 0.05). Migrant farmers accessed farmland primarily through rental (29%), borrowing from the community (26.5%), purchase (18.8%), and leasing (16%). Major challenges faced included limited access to loan (25.9%), high cost of farm input (20.8%), herdsmen incursions (15.8%), and poor road infrastructure (12.7%). The paper advocated for policy interventions to support migrant farmers' contributions to food production, including improved access to loans, subsidized farm inputs, rural road rehabilitation, and re-evaluation of security strategies to protect them.

Keywords: Agriculture, Food Production, Migrant Farmers, Rural Communities.

INTRODUCTION

Migration is a critical issue that is attracting worldwide attention because of its effects on spatial distribution of population and socio-economic development in both origins and destination. It denotes human movement across an international border or within a country, state or geographical region, which results in a temporary or permanent change of residence (UNESCO, 2008; Ogunmakinde *et al.*, 2015; Abizu, 2018). The important determinants of migration are the spatial distance, duration and purpose of movement

(de Haas, 2011). These factors depend on the realities at the origin and the destination of migrants.

Internal migration refers to human movement within a single geographical unit like a country or state. It is driven by factors such as education, economic opportunities, and security, but not by political reasons. Circular and repeat migration patterns are frequently observed in developing economies and among internal migrants. Several reasons may be adduced for migrants return back home: changing migration circumstances, economic

decline in their destination country, or increased income in their home country. For example, the economic collapse in Indonesia and Thailand between 1997 and 1998 triggered significant urban-to-rural and rural-to-urban return migration during the East Asia crisis. Another example is Ghanaian migrants returned from Nigeria in the mid-1980s due to economic improvements in Ghana. In Nigeria, rural-to-urban migration is common, motivated by wage differences, better perceived living conditions, and the presence of urban infrastructure, including electricity, roads, higher education, industries, and recreational facilities.

Recent urban-rural migration in Nigeria, is driven by rising crime and cost of living, highlights insufficient scholarly attention to urban displacement and contesting the city. Key drivers of urban-to-rural migration include job insecurity, retirement, and unaffordability of urban life, as identified by Adewale (2017). Agriculture contributed about 26.4 per cent to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2023 (NBS, 2024), it is regarded as the second-highest employer of labour, employing about 65 % of the country's labour force (Oyaniran, 2020). Small holder farmers constituted about 70 per cent of the labour force in the agricultural sector, contributing more than 70 per cent to non-oil export and provide over 80 per cent of the food needs of the country (IFAD, 2013). Migrant farmers are among the smallholders who engage in remunerated food crop production in a state where they are not indigenes (Martins and Taylor, 2014). A notable fact about migrant farmers is the frequency of return home, the duration of absence from home which vary widely from seasonal movements to short-term contract work, and continued sojourn until retirement to the homeland.

In 2018, approximately 600,000 farmers in Northern Nigeria were displaced by drought and flood, a situation exacerbated by ongoing population growth, diminishing arable land, land degradation, natural disasters, and violent land disputes. Without preventative measures, the UN projected that 25 million Nigerians could face severe food insecurity. This paper examined socio-economic characteristics, and pattern of farmers' migration to the rural communities of Kwara State, identify major push and pull factors responsible for their migration from place of origin to the rural communities, examine types of farmland ownership structure in the host communities and constraints to their agricultural production.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

MIGRATION: Migration is defined as the movement of people from an origin to a destination, involving a substantial break from social and cultural ties. Key drivers for migration include lack of employment, starvation, food shortages, political uncertainty, violence, crime, conflicts, and environmental issues. Conversely, factors such as perceived better job opportunities, improved education, enhanced security and safety, and gender equality attract individuals to destination locations (Olajide, 2019). Rural migration is a complex phenomenon driven by multifaceted economic and social developments, particularly stemming from the industrial revolution. This movement is characterized by resistance to poverty and an inclination to escape agricultural life and rural settings in favor of urban environments (Nagashima, 2018). According to Gollin *et al*, (2015), Global rural migration offers insights into socio-economic trends which have been resolved in advanced countries but still remains a significant and challenging issue in developing countries. It may continue posing

challenges for developing nations and the world at large if displacement of farmers are not addressed.

National Population Commission survey of 2010 reported that 10 per cent of Nigerians resided in states other than their states of origin and there were significant differences amongst the states with Ogun, Kwara, Osun, and Imo, having more than 10 per cent of their indigenes living in other states. The survey also found that 60 per cent of migrants lived in urban areas while 40 percent live in rural areas. The survey further revealed that states with 60 per cent of migrants living in rural areas are those with extensive agricultural activities, such as Akwa Ibom, Bauchi, Benue, Nasarawa, Jigawa, Kebbi and Kwara (Isiugo-Abanihe and IOM, 2014).

Rural Areas is defined by scholars as an open landmass with limited structures and a small population, primarily engaged in agriculture, with inhabitants often working on farms or ranches. These settlements include hamlets, villages, and small towns. In developing nations, rural inhabitants are frequently smallholder farmers working less than two hectares or involved in livestock raising (FAO, 2015). The achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals is central to African countries' development. Sustainable rural development is critical to a country's economic, social, and environmental viability. Because global poverty is overwhelmingly rural, it is critical for poverty eradication. Poverty has sub-regional and regional contexts that extend beyond the urban-rural divide (FAO, 2015). Coordination of rural development initiatives that contribute to sustainable livelihoods at the global, regional, national, and local levels is therefore critical, and there is much to be gained in the development of the rural areas especially in Nigeria.

MIGRANT FARMERS IN THE RURAL AREAS

Farming is the fabric of rural society and the primary economic activity in many countries around the world. Any abrupt and profound changes affecting the agricultural sector could have serious consequences on social and political stability of economically-developing countries. Agricultural production contributes significantly to rural development, particularly in countries where the oil sector is less economically significant. Migrants have played an important role in the development of labour markets in some developed economies. In European Union (EU) member-countries, for example, foreigners contributed to 50 per cent of total employment growth in countries such as Malta, Austria, Luxembourg, and Germany between the second quarter of 2013 and the first quarter of 2019 (Nickel *et al.*, 2019) in Zawojka and Siudek (2021).

Migrant farmers in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly Nigeria, migrate from places of economic stagnation to places of opportunity through agricultural practices (Waldinger, 2015). Migrant farmers in Nigeria exhibit specialisation, focusing either on crop cultivation (mono- or mix-cropping) or non-crop agricultural activities like livestock, poultry, beekeeping, and fisheries. Crop production necessitates more arable land compared to specialisations in livestock, poultry, bees, and fisheries. Diversification serves as a crucial survival strategy for these farmers. Migrant farmers generate income surpluses that enable investment in agricultural production and rural micro-enterprises. Despite specialisation, most continue as secondary occupations within or outside agriculture to supplement their primary income.

This paper is premised on the push and pull theory, modified by Beaumont et al. (1997) and Lee’s theory, to examine migration of farming populations. Push factors include unemployment, conflict, land degradation, and economic prospects, while pull factors include peace, security, employment opportunities, and economic prospects. Interference factors include distance, control prejudice, accommodation expenses, and fear of the unknown. Philip and Agbonlahor (2015) identified previous migration experience, household and community socioeconomic status, and other factors as key influences on migrants' decisions to settle permanently in rural communities as farmers. This article addresses the scarcity of research on internal migration, particularly rural-to-rural flows in Nigeria, by generating data on the migration

of farmers into rural communities of Kwara State, an agrarian state.

STUDY AREA

LOCATION: Kwara State, situated in Nigeria's North Central geopolitical zone, spans 36,825 square kilometers between 8°05' and 10°04' north latitude and 2°50' and 6°05' east longitude. It shares borders with Benin Republic to the west, Niger State to the north, Kogi State to the east, and Ekiti, Osun, and Oyo States to the south. Its strategic location, earning it the nickname ‘State of Harmony,’ facilitates access between northern and southern of the country’s lateral highway, making it accessible to migrant farmers (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of Kwara State (The Study Area)

Source: Produced by the Author, 2024

CLIMATE: Kwara State is characterised by a tropical climate with double rainfall maxima and a tropical wet and dry climate (Olanrewaju, 2010). The rainy season starts around March and ends in October within the year. The dry season normally starts in early October and

ends in March. The yearly rainfall, range from 1,000 to 1,500 mm. During rainy season, temperature ranges between 25° C and 29° C, except in July and August when cloud cover inhibits direct sunlight while temperature ranges between 33°

C and 34° C in the dry season. Seasonal farming is favored by these climatic conditions. Just like other farmers in the country, climatic conditions shape the pattern of internal migration and relatively good climate favours seasonal farming, and attracts migrant farmers to the state. Human migration is a response to both poverty and social deprivation, as well as an adaptation to climate change (Scheffran et al., 2012). Climatic elements such as temperature, radiation, precipitation, and humidity, among other factors, have a direct impact on agricultural production, which includes food crops, forestry, fisheries, and livestock, because atmospheric conditions determine their growth (Cheng et al., 2022). It also influences the migration decisions that migrant farmers make to survive, as they move in response to seasonal weather variations to places with favourable climatic conditions for agricultural production.

SOIL: Soil is a major asset for farmers and communities all over the world. Good soil produces good crops that provide a good income and allows farming families to thrive. The soil in Kwara State is ferruginous sandy-loam and clay-loam, both of which are rich in essential minerals for the production of cash and food crops. The ferruginous soil can be found beneath dry forest and savannah on acid crystalline bedrock rocks. It is a laterite soil that is brownish red and prone to water erosion and leaching. It is found between 100 and 250 cm beneath the surface, but its depth varies greatly (Dauda & Olayinka, 2024). Root, grain, and cash crops are grown in this soil. In rural areas, agricultural land use is the most common type of land use and an excellent resource for both crop and non-crop farming in Kwara State. Poultry, fishing, goat,

sheep, pigs, and bee-keeping are non-crop farming activities that provide supplementary revenue to farmers including migrants who engage in crop farming in the state.

RELIEF AND DRAINAGE: Kwara State features low to moderate topography, characterized by a few laterite-capped hills under 400 meters above sea level, categorized into highland, high plains, and low plains physiographic zones. The state boasts of an effective drainage system, primarily driven by the River Niger, with its largest tributary being the River Kampe. Other significant rivers include River Moshi, River Ero, River Osin, River Oyi, and Asa. Jebba Lake also plays a crucial role in the drainage network. Additionally, several dams and weirs provide vital water resources for domestic and agricultural use, among which the Asa and Aagba dams in Ilorin stand out, with capacities of four million and two million gallons per day, respectively (Kwara State Ministry of Water Resources report, 2011). This natural resources amongst other things attract migrant farmers into the State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study from which this paper was derived adopted survey approach with 4-stages sampling method. First stage was the selection of rural settlements where migrant farmers were living extracted from updated records of Agricultural Development Project (ADP) office, Ilorin Kwara State. The random selection covered settlements with population of at least 25 migrant farmers. A total of 2,281 migrant farmer household heads formed the frame. The 2nd stage, was selection of head of household of farmers from the frame. This was done using statistic Canada formula and computed as follows;

Compute n1 as generally required

$$n_1 = \frac{Z^2 P(1 - P)}{e^2} \dots\dots\dots \text{(equation 1)}$$

$$\frac{(1.96)^2 (.5) (.5)}{(.10)^2} = 96$$

Compute S with the formula $S = n_1 \frac{N}{N + n_1}$

Where S is sample size; e is desired margin of error (.10)²; Z – a value corresponding to a desired level of confidence (1.96); n1 = an estimate of the population variability which was obtained using P (1 – P); and P = 0.5 divided by (0 .10)², N = the population frame. The rationale for the choice of this method was to obtain population of migrant farmers

from the known population that was scientific and representative for the study (Statistic Canada, 2010; Miller and Brown, 2003).

For example, population frame of migrant farmers’ household head (HHs) in Asa LGA extracted from the record was 112, the sample size was estimated to be

$$S = 96 \times \frac{204}{204 + 96} = 65.28 \text{ (See Table 1).}$$

The 3rd stage was reconnaissance survey of the selected settlements and selection of the head of households using systematic random sampling technique. The 4th-stage was the actual administration of questionnaire to migrant farmers using structured

questionnaire checklist. In all, 825 sampled farmers were surveyed across the sixteen Local Government Areas (LGAs) of the state. Detail of sample size and number of head of household of migrant farmers selected is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sampled Population of Migrant Farmers in Selected Host Settlements by LGAs

S/N	L.GAs	Selected Migrant Farmers Settlements	Population of Migrant’s Head Households (HHs)	Computed Sampled Population	%
1	Asa	4	204	65	7.9
2	Baruten	4	114	52	6.3
3	Edu	3	250	69	8.4
4	Ekiti	8	100	49	5.9
5	Ifelodun	3	200	65	7.9
6	Ilorin East	3	79	43	5.2
7	Ilorin South	4	28	21	2.5
8	Ilorin West	3	38	27	3.3
9	Irepodun	3	281	71	8.6
10	Isin	3	57	35	4.2
11	Kaima	4	120	53	6.4
12	Moro	3	145	57	6.9
13	Offa	2	100	49	5.9
14	Oke Ero	3	106	50	6.1
15	Oyun	4	218	67	8.1
16	Patigi	2	112	52	6.3
	Total	56	2281	825	100.0

Source: Extracted and Computed from Migrant Farmers’ Record, ADP, 2024

The study processed copies of questionnaire retrieved with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Series 21) and qualitative information transcribed from in-depth interviews were used to achieve the study’s objectives as follows; (i) simple descriptive statistics such as frequency

tables, percentages, and flow charts were used to depict the spatial pattern of farmers relocation to Kwara State, (ii) multiple regression analysis was used to identify major push and pull factors of farmers’ migration to Kwara State. Thus, multiple regression model specification is expressed as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + b_k X_k + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 1 (Kotahari \& Garg, 2014).}$$

Y is the dependent variable representing latent factors (migrant period of migration), α is the intercept or constant term; b1, b2 ...bk are regression coefficients. Number of migrants per period of migration dependent on prevailing circumstances in the country is rationale for Y. Hence, this model estimated migrant farmer’s decision to migrate depends on underlying push factors whereby each

observed variable is a function of these factors together with a residual variate (X1, X2 Xk), while ε denotes error term. The independent variables are; X1 = land degradation, X2 = inadequate land for farming, X3 = lack of economic prospect at home, X4 = insecurity at home origin, X5 = herder invasion of farm, X6 = family feud,

X7 = communal conflict, X8 = unemployment, X9 = poor access to credit, X10 = insolvent at home, X11 = climatic problem, X12= lack of farm input, X13= land tenure problem, X14 = theft of farm produce, and X15 = flooding (number of farmers migrated as a result of annual flooding). On the other hand, the pull factors (attractions) to the rural host communities in the study area was modelled as;

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + b_k X_k + \epsilon$$

equation 2 (Kotahari & Garg, 2014).

Where Y represents number of migrant farmers in the current settlement destination. ($b_1 X_1, b_2 X_2, \dots, b_n$) represents independent variables as follows:

X1 = job opportunity in the rural host communities, X2 = peace and security prevailing in the rural host communities, X3= social harmony and integration, X4 = availability of fertile land, X5 = economic prospect (increase in income), X6 = increase in agricultural produce, X7= presence of prior migrant farmers' availability (kinsmen), X8 = flexible land tenure system, X9 = access to credit facilities, X10 = availability of farm inputs, and X11 = presence of tribe social group. The paper used statistical tools such as percentage and average, as well as multiple regression for data analysis to achieve the set objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

The paper explored the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of migrant farmers to achieve its objectives. It discovered

that 94.1% of migrant farmers were found in rural settlements, while 5.9% were found in sub-urban rural areas. Male head of household of migrant farmers constituted 89.2%, and females (10.8%). In terms of migrants' engagement in agriculture in the state, male household heads are more than female household heads. As for the age category of migrant farmers, the age range of 25-54 years represents a substantial proportion summed-up to 85%, and the mean age was 42 years. This indicates that majority of the migrant farmers fall within the active population age groups, and this is expected to have a considerable positive impact on host communities in terms of food crop production and agriculture labour supply, because young and vibrant middle-age population tends to be more productive in agriculture (FAO, 2014; Obisesan, 2019).

In terms of marital status, married respondent migrant farmers accounted for the majority (82.2%), followed by divorced (8.5%) and widow/widower 7.2% (Table 2). This result was likely due to hard labor required for agricultural production in the state just like other parts of Nigeria, which continue to rely significantly on crude implements and indigenous technologies. This influenced formation of family labour to minimize the cost of agricultural labour services. According to the findings, 27% of the migrant farmers studied were without formal education, 17% of them completed basic school, 11.5% completed secondary school, and only 2.2% had tertiary education. This indicates that majority of migrant farmers coming to Kwara State's rural settlements are without formal

education but have informal agricultural skills. This makes them rely on crude agricultural practices for a living and sustenance. This finding is consistent with earlier findings of

Afolayan *et al.* (2008); Agbonlahor and Philip (2015) who revealed that young ages dominate migration spaces in developing countries.

Table 2: Demographic and Social Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Category of Settlement		
Sub-urban	49	5.9
Rural	776	94.1
Total	825	100
Sex		
Male	736	89.2
Female	89	10.8
Total	825	100.0
Age Category		
15-19	5	0.6
20-24	25	3.0
25-29	72	8.7
30-34	112	13.6
35-39	106	12.8
40-44	162	19.6
45-49	172	20.8
50-54	82	9.9
55-59	33	4.0
60-64	19	2.3
65 and above	37	4.5
Total	825	100.0
Mean age = 42 years		
Marital Status		
Married	678	82.2
Single	70	8.5
Divorced/Separated	18	2.2
Widow/Widower	59	7.2
Total	825	100.0
Highest Level of Education Attained		
No formal Education	223	27.0
Quranic Education	105	12.7
Primary not completed	125	15.2
Primary Completed	148	17.9
Secondary School not Completed	95	11.5
Secondary Completed	111	13.5
Tertiary Education	18	2.2
Total	825	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

OCCUPATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

It discovered that respondents who engaged in crop cultivation accounted for 70.9% distantly followed by farm labour (11.2%) who were on the short-term informal farming jobs such as clearing bushes, weeding, making heaps and cutting of palm fruits. Migrants who specialized in livestock production constituted (10.3%) and fish farmers (2.8%) respectively, while food processors (2.7%), beekeepers (1.9%), and 0.02 % others which include hunters, palm fruit harvesters were amongst the migrants (Figure 2). This imply that migrant farmers who migrated to Kwara State did so, not only to make a living, but also to improve on their

well-being. This result confirmed the finding of earlier study that migration is widely regarded as an important component of livelihood coping strategies of escaping from poverty in developing countries (Stanley, 2018). Apart from farming, which was their major occupation, migrants also engage in secondary activities to supplement their income. The finding revealed that trading/business accounts for 35.2 % of secondary occupations, 23.9% of them were full time farmers, and 12.0% and 10.6% of the migrants engaged in snail keeping and okada (commercial motorcycle) riding. These activities were done to add to revenue generated from farming to increase their income and improve their living standard (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Major Occupations of Migrant Farmers
Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 3: Migrant Farmers' Secondary Occupations
Source: Field Survey, 2024

INCOME OF MIGRANT FARMERS BEFORE AND AFTER MIGRATION

Migrant farmers' ability to earn a living wage is critical to ensuring the viability and economic success of their stay in the new location. Figure 4 shows average income before migration. The paper discovered that average monthly income of migrant farmers varies, with majority population (72.8%) of them earning average monthly income less than then national minimum wage (N30,000) before migrating to Kwara State. This implies the low level of income amongst the farmers before migration. However, after migration, sampled farmers' average monthly earnings increased dramatically, with 74.2% of the farmers

earning more than the minimum wage. Using Nigeria's national minimum wage as a standard, 25.6% earned less than N30,000 per month after migration. Despite the challenges at the host community the number of migrant farmers earning less than minimum wage reduced while those earning more increased substantially (summed-up from Figure 5). This, when compare with average per capital cost of living indicates that migrant farmers earned more money in their destination than home of origins. This result is in tandem to the findings of Adeleke (2021) and Stanley (2018) who argued that people are motivated to escape poverty through migration as a result of potential opportunities in the new destinations.

Figure 4: Average Monthly Income of before Migration
 Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 5: Average Monthly Income after Migration
 Source: Field Survey, 2024

MIGRATION PATTERN OF FARMER’S SETTLEMENTS INTO KWARA STATE

This subsection identified the locational pattern of settlements where migrant farmers are living and working in Kwara State. The choice of where migrant farmers settled and engage in agriculture was influenced by several circumstances, including the presence of fertile land, the ease with which farmland may be

acquired, security and others. It discovered migrant farmers’ settlements are more prevalent in the southern part of the state than in the northern and central parts of the State. Figure 6 shows major settlements of migrant farmers. They are found in Irepodun (8.6%), Edu (8.4%), and Oyun (8.1%) while Ilorin South recorded (2.5%), Ilorin West (3.3%), and Isin LGAs (4.2%) had the lowest presence of relocated farmers.

Figure 6: Location of Settlement where Migrant Farmers are mostly found
Source: Field Survey, 2024

PATTERN OF MIGRATION OF FARMERS FROM HOME ORIGIN

The migration flow of farmers from home origin reveals a radial pattern with significant number of them coming from North Central, North East and NorthWest geopolitical zones. According to the finding, the state of origins with high number of migrant farmers were Benue (23.4%), Kebbi (15%), Sokoto (10.4%), Kogi (9%) and Nasarawa (8.2%). Apart from Sokoto and Kebbi from North West geopolitical zone, significant number of farmers from listed zones was likely attributed

to ongoing conflicts and insurgency. Other states with significant proportion were Delta State (5%), Kaduna, Borno and Yobe states (see Figure 7). The proportion of migrant farmers from aforementioned states relocated due to the unrest caused by activities of insurgents such as Boko Haram, bandits, herdsmen and kidnapers who have wreaked havoc on the people of these states and beyond over the past 20 years. According to the findings 23.4% of migrant farmers are from Benue state while 0.2% migrated from Oyo State. A total of 23 states experienced migration outflow of farmers to Kwara State. They lived and engage in farming activities.

Figure 7: Pattern of Migration of Farmers into Kwara State

Source: Field Survey, 2024

FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR MIGRATION OF FARMERS

According to the findings, the underline factors responsible for migration of farmers from their native homes are categorized push factors while on the other hand, the attractions for the choice of the host rural communities were named ‘pull factors. It was discovered that land degradation, inadequate farmland for farming, family feud, communal dispute, land tenure problem, lack of economic prospect at home or previous destination, herdsmen

invasion, poor access to credit, climatic problem, financial insolvent at home or previous place of residence, insecurity at home, lack of farm input and persistent theft of farm products were reported by the respondent migrants. Analysis using multiple regression model indicate that four factors were highly significant at (p-value < 0.05) as major influencing factors, they were; lack of economic prospect at home, flooding, family feud, insecurity at home, and herdsmen invasion of farms (see Table 3).

Table 3: Push Factors of Migration of Farmers from Home Origin

Multiple Regression Model		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B		
1	(Constant)	1971.72	260.9	.000
	Land degradation	0.186	.453	.650
	Inadequate farmland	1.038**	2.87	.004
	Lack of economic prospect at home	1.441**	4.65	.000
	Insecurity at home	1.285**	3.46	.001
	Herder’s invasion of farm	1.440**	3.36	.001
	Family feud	1.773**	4.38	.000
	Communal conflict	1.520*	2.33	.020
	Unemployment	1.073*	2.45	.014
	Poor access to credit	1.272	1.47	.142
	Insolvent (incurred debt)	-0.977	-.646	.518
	Climatic problem	0.146	.298	.766
	Lack of farm input	1.412	1.177	.240
	Land tenure problem	1.501**	2.363	.018
	Theft of farm produce	0.684	.936	.349
	Others, specify: flooding,	8.954**	5.104	.000

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Migrant farmers' decisions on where to settle in rural communities of Kwara State were influenced by various pull factors including job availability, peace and security, social harmony and integration, fertile farmland, economic prospects like increased income, greater agricultural produce, the presence of previous migrants, a flexible land tenure system, access to credit, and the availability of farm inputs. Regression analysis of factors for the choices of rural settlements for their farming activity

reveals four factors were highly significant. These are peace and security ($p=0.000$), availability of fertile land ($p=0.000$), a flexible land tenure system ($p=0.001$), and availability of farm input ($p=0.015$) see Table 4. The availability of arable farmland, coupled with flexible land tenure and peace, are essential for farming families, particularly ethnic nationalities interested in farming, to remain in their communities across the country.

Table 4: Pull Factors for Migrant’s Choice of the Host Destinations

Multiple Regression Model	Standardised Coefficients		
	B	T	Sig.
1 (Constant)	1.054	3.445	.001
Job opportunity	-0.013	-.590	0.555
Peace and security	0.083**	4.669	0.000
Social harmony and integration	0.035	1.094	0.274
Availability of fertile land for farming	0.073**	4.047	0.000
Economic prospect (increase in income)	0.039	1.655	0.098
Increase in agricultural produce	0.025	.614	0.540
Presence of prior migrant availability	-0.031	-1.004	0.316
Flexible land tenure system	0.192**	3.252	0.001
Access to credit facilities	-0.019	-.314	.753
Availability of farm input	0.161*	2.450	0.015
Others, specify:	-.066	-.684	.494

** Significant at p-value <0 .05%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

FARMLAND OWNERSHIP STRUCTURE IN THE HOST COMMUNITIES

It was discovered that 88.8% of migrants owned farms, while 11.2% did not. Migrants’ farmers were categorized as crop or non-crop farmers, and non-owners worked as farm laborers. It was also found that newly arrived migrant farmers often began as casual laborers but transitioned to permanent migrants when the host settlement environment proved suitable for agriculture. Farmland size among migrant farmers ranges from under one hectare to 10 hectares. The average holding was two hectares for 41% of these farmers, while 27%

of those specializing in crop production own less than one hectare. Despite this they contribute meaningfully to food crops production in their host settlements.

Migrants seeking for farmland access typically lack automatic rights, regardless of duration of his/her stay in the host community. To obtain farmland, they usually need to join a household or secure vouching from indigene or community chief in the host settlement. Specifically, migrant farmers acquired farmland through renting (29%), followed by borrowing communal farmland (26.5%), purchase farmland (18.8%), and leasing

farmland (16.1%). These land acquisition methods showed no insignificant differences across the sixteen local government areas, with renting and borrowing being the most frequent practices. It was discovered that Migrant farmers' agricultural production and

crop choice is constrained by common methods of farmland acquisition. These methods restrict them from planting of permanent crops that are more profitable crops like cocoa, coffee, and cashews, palm tree which require longer growing seasons, forcing migrants to focus on seasonal food crops.

Figure 8: Access to Farmland Structure by Migrant Farmers
Source: Field Survey, 2024

CONSTRAINTS TO MIGRANT FARMER'S AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

This paper identified quite number of challenges facing migrant farmers in rural communities of Kwara, including difficulty in obtaining loan for farming (25.9%), high costs of fertilizers and implements (20.8%), Fulani invasions of farms (15.8%), and issues with farmland access (13%), poor road conditions (12.7%) and unstable rainfall (9.8%). Other less prevalent problems like farm product theft (1.7%) and limited access to extension services (0.2%). These challenges are surmountable if

there is political will by the government. These constraints negatively impacted on both agricultural production and the social and economic well-being of migrant farmers. Poor rural road conditions hinder the transportation of farm produce, especially during the rainy season, making farmers to depend on commercial motorcycle riders with limited carrying capacity. This reliance increases transportation costs, reduces farmers' income, and adversely affects migrants overall well-being. Constant invasions of farms by herdsmen hinder agricultural production in the state, with no effective policy measures addressing the issue.

Table 5: Major Constraints to Migrants' Agricultural Production in the Host Settlements

Major Constraints	Frequency	%
Problem of acquiring more land for farming	107	13.0
Problem of getting loan for farming	214	25.9
Bad road condition	105	12.7
Theft of farm produce before harvesting	14	1.7
Unstable rainy period affect production	81	9.8
No access to extension services	2	0.2
Herdsmen invasion	130	15.8
High cost of fertilisers and implements	172	20.8
Total	825	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper examined socioeconomic characteristics of migrant farmers in Kwara State, Nigeria, their migration reasons, destination attractions, farmland ownership structures, and challenges facing them. It has contributed to a better understanding of the dynamism of rural-to-rural migration, as well as knowledge of migration and development in agriculture, particularly in Kwara State. The following are the recommendations;

- i) The problem of insufficient farmland for migrants in their home regions can be resolved through implementation of land reform policies that have been delayed for two decades. Land hoarding, where individuals possess unused hectares while willing farmers lack land, hinders agricultural production. Consequently, land acquisition policies across all states should be revised to prioritize smallholder farmers by increasing

flexibility.

- ii) Internal migration is significantly driven by insecurities such as herdsmen invasions, banditry, kidnapping, cattle rustling, and the theft of agricultural produce. Farmers are migrating to states offering greater peace, impacting on receiving states like Kwara, by increasing demand for arable land, causing problems in rural communities, especially for crop farmers. Consequently, security strategies in the country require re-evaluation.
- iii) Internal migration in Nigeria, encompassing inter-state and rural-to-rural movements, is challenging to manage. This problem is exacerbated by insecurity and terrorist activities resulting to discrimination against migrant farmers. Consequently, the government is urged to initiate a campaign to combat all forms of discrimination against migrants within Nigeria.

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